

Hypsometric Analysis of Patalganga River Basin using Geographic Information System.

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Abstract:

Hypsometric curve is important watershed health indicator and reveals the stages of watershed development (Old, mature and Young). Hypsographic curve accessed using graph of measures contour intervals and contain area by empirical formula i.e. Relief-elevation ratio method has used for this study. Digital elevation model usually used for watershed analysis. DEM Data has been downloaded and processed to generate or delineate the watershed using GIS software. This article presents methodologies used for watershed analysis. The main contribution of this work lies in analysis of relief- elevation ratio in Patalganga river basin. The hypsometric integral value for Patalganga river basin lies in the middle of 0.30 to 0.59, the stages of geomorphic development only mature stage is identified. This study will help the geographers or planners to bear the health of watershed.

Keywords: Hypsometric Curve, Watershed, Patalganga River Basin, Elevation, Area.

Introduction:

Worlds 29% continent is divided in to Mountain(26%), Plateau(33%), Plain(41%) and 71% Water is divided in to continental shelf 8.6%, Continental slope8.5%, deep sea plain 75.9% and oceanic deep 7% according to height. Height of continental part and depth of parts from sea level is undergoing continuously changing due to endogenic and exogenic forces. Hence hypsometric or hypsometric curve is changing. Due to Volcanic eruption, Tectonic activities, sedimentation and sea level changing and compression. A graph used to indicate the proportion of the area of the earth surface at various elevation above or depth below a given datum, such as sea level. The height or depths being shown on vertical axis, the land area on the horizontal. The automated GIS approach for hypsometric analysis enables the hydrological modelling community which has potential in increase the predictive power and transferability like rainfall runoff model^[5]. Hypsometric analysis is relationship of horizontal cross section total river basin area to elevation. Three methods Integration of hypsometric Curve (HC), Planimetre and Elevation- relief ratio relationship can be used to compute the hypsometric analysis. Out of the three the elevation- relief ratio method was the best because it's easiest and minimal time without any equipment^[11]. The major difference in surface of the planet portion 80% for Venus and 50% for Earth. Which is half as steep slope for Venus as for the earth^[10]. This study presents an automatic procedure using GIS software to achieve hypsometric analysis using DEM data. Although automation is implemented using ARC Map it can be easily adopted to other environment.

Study Area:

Asia is the Largest Continent on the earth. Raigad District is in the western part of Maharashtra. It lays between 17° 15' North to 19° 50' N. Latitude and 72° 51' East to 73° 40' E. Longitude. The Ulhas Patalganga, Bhogawati, Amba, Kundalika and Savitri etc are the Major Rivers in Raigad District. Raigarh district is close to the sea therefore the climate of

the District is hot and humid. The Patalganga River has its source in the Khandala portion of the Sahyadri scarp. The Ulhas Patalganga, Bhogawati, Amba, Kundalika and Savitri etc are the Major Rivers in Raigad District. Raigarh district is close to the sea therefore the climate of the District is hot and humid [Figure1].

Elevation Relief Ratio: DEM data easily available in two formats i.e. Raster and Vector, for this study Raster format has been downloaded and converted in to vector format. Data has been reclassified according to relief Hypsographic curve and plotted graph. Contour intervals for height and area analyzed by empirical formula i.e. Relief-elevation ratio method has used for this study. Digital elevation model usually used for watershed analysis. DEM Data has been processed to generate or delineate the watershed using GIS software. The Elevation-Relief ratio (E) Relationship method has adopted and the main parameters are elevation and area.

Result and Discussion:

Result of the study area are discussed under following sub-headings:

Patalganga River Basin and Area: Advance Remote sensing data and open source GIS tools process become easier than conventional method to study HC^[4]. Adverse effect of hypsometric curve to coarse spatial resolution DEM raster data has used to define the drainage network and delineated the watershed^[4]. The area of the watersheds above certain elevation is the sum of the area above the zone of above the elevation. Patalganga River has 15 sub watershed of Bhogawati, and Amba, etc. are major rivers in figure2. Its total watershed which resulted in delineated watershed area is 2008.41 sq. kms [Table1]. Figure 3 shows that the Average Area of Patalganaga river basin has ranges from lowest 50-100 and 201-250 sq. kms. There are 5 sub basins ranges at lowest area (50-100 sq. kms.), 4 sub basins ranges at lowest mid (101-150 sq. kms.), 4 sub basins ranges at middle area (151-200 sq. kms.) and 2 subbasins ranges at highest area (201-250 sq. kms.). The hypsometric integral study is essential for watershed because its value can be an indicator of the erosion from the watershed system^[11].

Digital Elevation Model and Elevation:

For DEM data model, hypsometric curve can be obtained using adjacent contour lines and frequency polygon has calculated. The area of the zone is the sum of all cells can be easily calculated by zonal statistic function of raster GIS^[7]. The statistic for Patalganga river basin highest elevation is 876 mts. and represents through red color [Figure4]. Hypsometric analysis is also known as area elevation model. It is analyzed the relation between the area of horizontal cross section of watershed and correspond elevation. It has been termed drainage basin relief graph is considered as an indicator of basin health^[11]. Elevation relief method can be adjusted as the most resourceful method for estimating hypsometric analysis^[11]. DEM was reclassified as per the elevation using software. Highest altitude is 870 mts. in Patalganga river basin. To study Elevation of Patalganga River Basin the entire data set reclassifies based on natural brakes method. The average elevation area 36.79% area resulted below sea level and 63.21% area shows above mean sea level. The area above MSL 54% area is plain and remaining area (approximately 4%) area is hilly area.

Figure 2: Location Map of Study Area

Figure 3: Patalganga River Sub-Basins

Figure 4: Patalganga Rivers Sub basin Area

Figure 5: DEM Patalganga River Basin.

Figure 6: Elevation of Patalganga River Basin

Table 1: Elevation and Area Ratio of Patalganga River Basin

ID	Elevation		Area (in Sq. Kms)	Per. (%)	c.f.
	From	To			
1	-255	-142.5	35.25	1.75	1.75
2	-142.5	-30	739.07	36.80	38.55
3	-30	82.5	720.22	35.86	74.41
4	82.5	195	276.08	13.75	88.16
5	195	307.5	121.96	6.07	94.23
6	307.5	420	61.70	3.07	97.30
7	420	532.5	23.92	1.19	98.50
8	532.5	645	19.65	0.98	99.47
9	645	757.5	10.43	0.52	99.99
10	757.5	870	0.15	0.01	100.00
Total			2008.41	100.00	

Figure 7: Hypsometric Curve Patalganga River Basin

Figure 8: Hypsometric Graph Patalganga River

Hypsometric Curve (HC): HC is distinguished into 3 terms i.e. concave upward curve, concave convex group and concave downward and convexity [8]. HC of the earth contains relevant information about the existence of plate tectonic, visible in the part of representing the escarpments and connecting the lighter continental area to the heavier oceanic area [3]. Simple and rapid methods can be used for hypsometric curves of basin. The techniques may be used for measuring most basin properties that involve areal measurement [2]. Hypsometric curve gives the hypsometric integral proved mathematically that E is defined as Integration of hypsometric curve is given in equation $E = \frac{(\text{Elev. Aver.} - \text{Elev. Min.})}{(\text{Elev. Max.} - \text{Elev. Min.})}$. It is observed from hypsometric curve the watershed is attaining the concave slope and equilibrium the mature stage ($E=54.74\%$) [figure6]. Table 1 shows Elevation and area ratio of Patalganaga River basin. The highest elevation is 870 mts. Total area of Patalganga River basin is 2008.41 sq. kms. Approximatelt 74% area has been occupied below 82.5mts. Patalganga Rivers most of area (74%) is covered with plain and depth and remaining approximately (26%) area occupying with small hills [Figure7]. Referring to figure 6 and 7 Patalganga River basin is in equilibrium or mature stage of common geomorphic processes. It was applied by formula E the His value was 54.74% and this mean that Patalganga River basin is in mature stage.

Research Gaps, Status and Future Trends:

This study endeavors to bridge this gap. The innovative approach is that, whole data related to Elevation and area of watershed is generated through GIS software. A situation or state of development of watersheds is going to help relief and altitude. The study resents the applications of geomorphic development is self-generated. The study reveals that there is need of study to search our neighbor planets like the Mars, Venus and Moon.

Recommendation:

Patalganga river basin has having HI is 0.5474so this value is >0.5 (i.e. approaching youthful stage) need construction both vegetative and mechanical soil and water conservation structure to arrest sediment load and conserve water for integrated watershed management.

Conclusion:

Integration of hypsometric Curve (HC), Planimetre and Elevation- relief ratio relationship can be used to compute the hypsometric analysis. Out of those three the elevation- relief ratio method is best for Hypsometric analysis. The study reveals that GIS software's is most important to hypsometric analysis. Those software's reveals good performance in preparation of different DEM maps specially calculation of Hypsometric Curve. The result of hypsometric curve shows that the Patalganga river basin is in mature stage. More than 40% area is under mean sea level and remaining 60 % area is above mean sea level in study area. Means there are 54% area is covered by plain, 40% is covered by water and 4% area is covered by small hills.

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